

METHODOLOGY OF USING MOBILE AND GAME EXERCISES IN THE TRAINING OF YOUNG FOOTBALL PLAYERS

Tursunkulov Mansur Mahmud ogli

Teacher, National Research University "Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers".

Abstract: This article describes the development of dexterity, grasping, aiming, logical and quick thinking qualities of young football players with the help of mobile games and game exercises, as well as the views of experts on this topic.

Key words: action games, football, psychophysiological factors, movement amplitude, game exercises.

INTRODUCTION

Games provide great educational opportunities for the formation of qualities of determination, courage and will. It is also evident in the analysis of some features of psychological processes such as intuition, perception, attention, memory [N.Rakhmatov. A. Sattarov. 5]. Various actions in action games have a positive effect on the emotions of young players. Most importantly, qualities such as dexterity, dribbling, aiming, which are important in football, are improved. During the game, children run, jump, crawl, and as a result, their muscles and sensory organs develop. As a result of this, the skills of being able to subordinate their decisions to the rules of the game are formed and refrain from rude behavior, to act quickly when necessary, to think quickly and to find a way to get out of a difficult situation. will learn.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

A number of studies have shown that specially selected action games are the

most suitable form for learning and developing individual characteristics, not only during qualifying, but also during the training of young players. Techniques like these mean that the movement skills necessary for a player are mastered, refined and strengthened. As a result, it becomes possible to use them in the game, when fighting for the ball.

The elements of action games and sports games are one of the most important means of training skilled players, and according to a number of experts, they are the basis for easy learning of game methods. Games involve correct repetition and improvement of actions. In this regard, the motor development performed by the player during the game creates a basis for the coach to conduct the right physical training.

"The game was born with the child as if it were an idea, it became his companion or friend. But we think it's good that it will last for a long time. "The game attracts people's attention due to its huge and sometimes invisible educational side and wide pedagogical possibilities," said one of the experts. The game provides great educational opportunities for the formation of the qualities of determination, courage and will. Also, it is clearly invisible in the analysis of some features of psychological processes such as intuition, perception, attention, memory.

DISCUSSION

Various actions in action games have a positive effect on the emotions of young players, strengthen their will, develop courage and independence. The most important thing is that the qualities of dexterity, aiming, aiming and logical thinking, which are important in football, are improved. During the game, children run, jump, crawl, and as a result, their muscles and sense organs are formed. As a result, the skills of subordinating one's decisions to the rules of the game are refined, one refrains from rude behavior, one is able to act quickly when necessary, think quickly and find a way out of a difficult situation. grows. In the

process of training based on active games, young players develop their movement, skills and abilities quickly, and their amplitude of movement and assessment skills improve. The ability to analyze the action, to distinguish certain qualities in it, develops. As a result of the action, he begins to understand that it depends on the qualities of its performance. In order to achieve good results, he begins to perform actions with endurance. All this allows basic movements, exercise techniques.

RESULTS

Along with simple and moderately complex games with 7-10-year-old children, if the children are sufficiently prepared, then more complex games can be played as a team [A .Sattarov,3]. In such a situation, a team game is formed, the ability to understand each other develops.

"The third is a plus." 10-12 people will participate

Preparation. A circle with a diameter of 8-10 meters is drawn in the center of the field. The players are in pairs and stand in a row around the circle at a distance of 1-2 meters. The coach appoints two starters: a runner and a receiver.

Game details. At the sound signal, the fleeing person tries to get away from the person who is catching up, then unexpectedly stops in front of one of the pair. The player standing behind starts running away. If the player standing behind becomes the catcher, the game will be more interesting.

Variant. Those who stand in pairs put their legs wide, and the running player must crawl between the legs.

The goal. The game helps to improve the skills of running, reaction speed and fast running, agility.

"We hunt rabbits." 10-16 people participate

Preparation. A circle with a diameter of 10 meters is drawn in the center of the hall (field).

The participants in the game are divided into two teams of 6-8 people. One

of the teams ("rabbits") stands in a circle. "Hunters" with a volleyball stand outside the circle line.

Game details. According to the sound signal, the "hunters" do not enter the circle and try to touch the ball to the "rabbits", in this situation the "rabbits" run to a safe place in the circle. The "rabbits" who hit the ball leave the game and begin to perform one of the four pre-arranged additional exercises.

The game continues until all "rabbits" are knocked out. After Shin, the teams exchange places. The team that eliminated the players of the opponent's team from the game in the shortest or specified time (for example, in three minutes) is considered the winner.

The rule of the game. "Hunters" do not have the right to set foot in the circle (does not count forward). The "rabbit" that has left the line of the circle is out of the game. If the ball touches any part of the body except for the head (the ball can be returned with the head) (it does not count if it comes from the ground or a partner), it is considered to have hit a "rabbit". In this game, it is necessary to achieve team actions by passing the ball to each other.

Variant. If the ball hits from a kick, the "rabbits" are out of the game.

The goal. The game strengthens the skills of catching, passing and throwing the ball. Improves orientation, reaction, resourcefulness (choosing a place), agility, accuracy of movement.

"Wolf in his lair". 10-12 people play

Preparation. Two parallel lines with an interval of 80-100 cm ("hive") are drawn in the center of the field. Two "houses" are drawn on opposite sides of the hall (field). One or two starters ("wolves") are selected to settle in the "nest". The rest ("rabbits", "lambs", "goats") stand behind the line of one of the houses.

Game details. At the signal, the "animals" try to run to another house, to their "mother". In this way, they jump from "nest" to another. "Wolves" try to touch them. Those who are caught perform an additional physical load (for example, 10

pull-ups and 10 sit-ups) and return to the players. Whoever does not get caught even once is considered the winner.

The rule of the game. Passes will be only at the signal. It is not possible to land on the "nest". "Wolves" have no right to leave their dens.

Those caught (stopped) or turned back in front of the "nest" are considered caught. Maneuvering in front of the "nest" is allowed, but it is necessary to jump over it. The number of distances between lines and "wolves" can be increased.

The goal. The game helps to improve running, long jump, maneuvering, develops orientation, ingenuity, bravery.

"Who is faster." 4-10 people play.

Preparation. A circle with a diameter of 10-12 meters is drawn in the center of the field, pillars are installed to go around the corners of the hall. Players with the ball stand in a circle.

Game details. According to the sound signal, the players voluntarily wrestle with the ball, trying to keep their coach in sight. with (throwing the ball) they run towards the nearest post, go around it and return to the circle. The last two players (late) go to the "improvement" area and fulfill the task of the coach. The game starts from the beginning. Those who remain in the circle are declared winners.

The rule of the game. If the ball crosses the circle line during the scrum, the offender will receive the first warning. After the second warning, this player moves to the "improvement" area. Participants should not touch someone else's ball or push the opponent with their hands. During training, the coach can change his position.

Variant. Instead of fighting, you can feint the ball and push it with stops.

The goal. The game improves technical elements in the conditions of a complex competition, develops agility, orientation in space, speed of reaction to visual signals.

"Faster to the flags." 10-16 people play

Preparation. Two parallel lines are drawn on opposite sides of the field. One of them is "own house", the other is "foreign house". A pole is installed 8-10 meters away from "own house". Players are divided into two equal teams. According to the result of the draw, the players of one team (for example, those in white clothes) will receive one volleyball or soccer ball.

Game details. The number one player (A, G) of the teams who has the ball kicks the ball from the "home" line with the arch of his foot towards the "alien home", and he quickly starts towards the post. , bypasses it and returns to the "other house". Players in black uniforms must catch the ball and try to touch the ball to the running player individually or at the expense of each other.

The rule of the game. As soon as the player of the opposing team (A, G) catches the ball (it is not possible before that), his partners can go to the upper side to receive the ball "from their house". The player who hits the ball gets a point. After all players occupy the initial position, the second player (B, D, then B, E) enters the game. After a certain time (5th minute) the teams exchange places. The player with the lowest number of points is declared the winner.

The goal. The game develops quickness, agility, coordination of movements, improves the technique of kicking the ball with the arch of the foot, catching the ball, forms a team game.

"For the opponent's ball". 6-10 people play.

Preparation. Players are divided into two teams of 3-5 people.

Game details. At the signal, the first players kick as far as possible into the "field" with the ball of their feet and move towards the opponent's ball. The player who takes his place first gets 1 point, the second player gets 0 points. Then, according to a certain signal, other pairs of players kick the ball, etc. The team with the most points is the winner.

The rule of the game. After hitting the ball, it is not possible to touch your own ball again, to destroy the opponent.

The goal. The game helps to improve the skill of hitting hard, develops strength and quickness.

Mixed relay: 8-meter sprint - stop - jump as if hitting the ball with the head - 5-meter sprint - push the ball "mock-like" - run back to the starting point. Breathing for 2 minutes (4 times of 30 seconds). Voluntary ball fighting

Mixed relay race: running - jumping over 3 hurdles in athletics - running around the flags as a snake - running for 30 meters.

Jumping, long jump and 25-meter hurdles relay

Running, gymnastic chair running, jumping and hurdling or step-by-step relay

"Mock-like" relay with two balls Pushing the basketball and moving until it hits the net, catching the ball and running to the starting point.

CONCLUSION

In the process of training based on action games, movement skills and competencies are quickly formed in young players, amplitude of movement, and evaluation skills are improved. The ability to analyze the action, to distinguish certain qualities in it, develops. As a result of the action, he begins to understand that it depends on the qualities of his performance. In order to achieve good results, he begins to perform actions with endurance. All this makes it possible to perform basic movements and exercise techniques.

References.

1. B.Nigmatov, F.Ho`jayev, K.Rahimqulov. Sport o`yinlari. Toshkent ilm ziyo. 2007 yil
2. T.S. Usmonxo`jayev, O. `Tursunov Jismoniy tarbiya nazariyasi va uslubiyoti». Tashkent O`qituvchi.. 2004 yil.
3. A.,Sattarov.,M.B.Aliyev, T.S.Usmonxo`jayev, X.X.Sagdiyev. Sport o`yinlari-Futbol. Toshkent 2012. Ilm ziyo.
4. Футбол дарслик ЎЗЖТИ нашрети 2006 й.